

Stability Analysis and Backward Bifurcation of Malaria Model

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Abstract

In this study, we examined a fuzzy SIR model for malaria transmission. To find stability analysis and fuzzy basic reproduction numbers of the virus spread, we established two equilibrium points. Dynamical systems techniques are used to examine the model, and the results show that the backward bifurcation occurs for a certain range of values.

Keywords: SIR Epidemic model, Stability Analysis, Backward Bifurcation.

Introduction

Malaria is a preventable and treatable disease that continues to have a devastating impact on the health and livelihood of people around the world. In 2022, there were an estimated 241 million new cases of malaria and 627000 malaria-related deaths in 85 countries.

World malaria day 2022 will be marked under the theme “Harness innovation to reduce the malaria disease burden and save lives”. Though different measures are being used globally to control malaria, no single tool is sufficient to solve the problem of malaria. Innovating new tools in different fields including vector control interventions and insecticides, improved diagnostics, and more effective anti-malarial medicines and other tools is essential to Achi achieve in global elimination targets.

In this paper we have discussed the phenomenon of backward bifurcation does not arise depending on vaccination coverage and the efficacy of the vaccine (RoumenAngueloetel.at-2014)

Yakuzai Xue et.al have highlighted the causes of founding that backward bifurcation occurs if the capacity is small. it is also found that the exists bistable endemic equilibrium is the capacity is low (YakXuexue et.al-2012).

The paper presents ed mathematical model for bacterial meningitis to include de nonlinear recovery rate and show instances of forwarding & backward bifurcation. The potential extensions of the model are likewise examining Joshuaus Kiddy K.Asamoah . an l-2015). Isac Mwangi Wang et. al(2020) Stud by varying a bifurcation are generally which they n epidemiological model is usually the so-called R_0 .but R_0 is nevertheless varied aa bifurcation

parameters. Kaiming Bi et.al (2020), have analyzed the stability and bifurcation by changing the closed population system to an open system. Our computational result suggests continuous optimal control strategies applications. Xuzhang and Xianning Liu's (2008), wave study to develop a backward bifurcation wittakeske place when this delayed effect for treatment is str o, ng and decreasing the infective coefficient are all valid methods of control of the disease.

The authors have constructed SEIR-SEI mathematical model by considering a few parameters as fuzzy numbers, the main objective of this paper is to control the spread of the virus by computing the reproduction number (Sweatha Selvakumar et.al-2022). As discussed in the n Fuzzy SIR-epidemic model for transmission of malaria (Monisha Pandiyan et.al-2022), we extend the work with h existence of backward bifurcation. In this paper, the main is focus on Stability Analysis and backward bifurcation to study the fuzzy SIR model in Malaria.

The study presented a mathematical model for bacterial meningitis that showed in forward and reverse bifurcation as well as a nonlinear recovery rate. The model's potential extensions are also looked at. Joshua Kiddy Asamoah et.al)

Fuzzy SIR Model:

The model is defined by the spread of malaria diseases (Monisha Pandiyan et.al 2022).

$$\frac{dS_p}{dt} = \mu_p - \frac{\beta_p(\phi)S_p I_m}{N_p} + \varepsilon_p R_p - \sigma_p S_p$$

$$\frac{dI_p}{dt} = \frac{\beta_p(\phi)S_p I_m}{N_p} - (\gamma_p(\phi) + \delta_p + \sigma_p)I_p$$

$$\frac{dR_p}{dt} = \gamma_p(\phi)I_p - \varepsilon_p R_p - \sigma_p S_p$$

$$\frac{dS_m}{dt} = \mu_m - \frac{\beta_m(\phi)S_m I_p}{N_p} - \sigma_m S_m$$

$$\frac{dI_m}{dt} = \frac{\beta_m(\phi)S_m I_p}{N_p} - \sigma_m I_m$$

------(1)

Stability Analysis:

In this part, we determine the prerequisites for endemic and disease-free local equilibrium stability. To start the stability study, we first need to locate the DFE and EE sites as well as a fundamental reproduction number.

i)The DFE obtained as $D_0 = (\frac{\mu_p}{\sigma_p}, 0, 0, \frac{\mu_m}{\sigma_m}, 0)$

ii) The EE obtained as $D_1 = (\frac{\sigma_m \mu_p + \sigma_p \beta_m I_p^*}{\sigma_p \sigma_m}, \frac{\gamma_p}{\sigma_p + \varepsilon_p}, \frac{\mu_m N_p}{\sigma_m N_p + \beta_m I_p^*}, \frac{\beta_m \mu_m I_p^*}{\sigma_m (\sigma_m N_p + \beta_m I_p^*)})$

iii)The system is determined using the next generation matrix method [].to deter

determined $R_0 = \frac{\beta_p(\phi)\beta_v \mu_v \sigma_p}{\sqrt{\mu_v \sigma_v^2 (\gamma_p(\phi) + \delta_p + \sigma_p)}}$

Theorem:1

The DFE points $D_0 = (\frac{\pi}{x}, 0, 0, 0)$ is unstable when $R_0 > 1$ and locally asymptotically stable for $R_0 < 1$.

Proof:

Using the Jacobian matrix of the system of equation (1), one may determine the stability of the disease's free equilibrium.

$$J(P_0) = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{\beta_p I_m}{N_p} & 0 & \varepsilon_p & 0 \\ \frac{\beta_p I_m}{N_p} & -(\gamma_p + \delta_p + \sigma_p) & 0 & 0 \\ -\sigma_p & \gamma_p & -\varepsilon_p & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{\beta_m S_m}{N_p} & 0 & -\sigma_m \\ 0 & \frac{\beta_m S_m}{N_p} & 0 & \frac{\beta_m I_p}{N_p} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$|J - \mu I| = 0$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} -\frac{\beta_p I_m}{N_p} - \mu & 0 & \varepsilon_p & 0 \\ \frac{\beta_p I_m}{N_p} & -(\gamma_p + \delta_p + \sigma_p) - \mu & 0 & 0 \\ -\sigma_p & \gamma_p & -\varepsilon_p - \mu & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{\beta_m S_m}{N_p} & 0 & -\sigma_m - \mu \\ 0 & \frac{\beta_m S_m}{N_p} & 0 & \frac{\beta_m I_p}{N_p} - \mu \end{pmatrix} = 0$$

Therefore, $\mu = \frac{\beta_p I_m}{N_p}, (\gamma_p + \delta_p + \sigma_p), \varepsilon_p, \sigma_m$

$$\mu^5 + A_1 \mu^4 + A_2 \mu^3 + A_3 \mu^2 + A_4 \mu + A_5 = 0 \tag{2}$$

Routh-Hurwitz criteria (2) states that the system of equations is locally asymptotically stable since its roots are negative. The disease-free equilibrium point for the system is hence locally asymptotically stable if $R_0 < 1$.

Theorem:2

The endemic equilibrium points $P_0 =$, when $R_0 < 1$ and unstable when $R_0 > 1$ is locally asymptotically stable.

Proof:

To obtain the stability of the endemic equilibrium Using the Jacobian matrix of the system of equation (2), i.e $|J - \mu I| = 0$. As a result, if $R_0 > 1$, the system's endemic equilibrium point will be locally asymptotically stable.

Backward Bifurcation of Analysis:

In this-cases, we found the derive of the conditions for backward bifurcation by using the theory of central manifold.

The following system is

$$\dot{x}_1 = \mu_p - \frac{\beta_p(\phi) S_p I_m}{N_p} + \varepsilon_p R_p - \sigma_p S_p$$

$$\dot{x}_2 = \frac{\beta_p(\phi) S_p I_m}{N_p} - (\gamma_p(\phi) + \delta_p + \sigma_p) I_p$$

$$f_3 = \gamma_p(\phi) I_p - \varepsilon_p R_p - \sigma_p S_p$$

$$f_4 = \mu_m - \frac{\beta_m(\phi) S_m I_p}{N_m} - \sigma_m S_m$$

$$f_5 = \frac{\beta_m(\phi) S_m I_p}{N_m} - \sigma_m I_m \tag{3}$$

The Jacobian matrix after linearizing (3) around the DFE is given as

$$J = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{\beta_p I_m}{N_p} - \sigma_p & 0 & \varepsilon_p & 0 & -\frac{\beta_p S_p}{N_p} \\ \frac{\beta_p I_m}{N_p} & -(\gamma_p + \delta_p + \sigma_p) & 0 & 0 & \frac{\beta_p S_p}{N_p} \\ -\sigma_p & \gamma_p & -\varepsilon_p & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{\beta_m S_m}{N_p} & 0 & -\sigma_m & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\beta_m S_m}{N_p} & 0 & \frac{\beta_m I_p}{N_p} & -\sigma_m \end{pmatrix} \tag{4}$$

The following systems of equations (4) and, we obtain the right eigenvector,

$$\left(-\frac{\beta_p I_m}{N_p} - \sigma_p\right) a_1 + \varepsilon_p a_3 - \frac{\beta_p S_p}{N_p} a_5 = 0$$

$$\frac{\beta_p I_m}{N_p} a_1 - (\gamma_p + \delta_p + \sigma_p) a_2 - \frac{\beta_p S_p}{N_p} a_5 = 0$$

$$-\sigma_p a_1 + \gamma_p a_2 - \varepsilon_p a_3 = 0$$

$$-\frac{\beta_m S_m}{N_p} a_2 - \sigma_m a_4 = 0$$

$$\frac{\beta_m S_m}{N_p} a_2 + \frac{B_m I_p}{N_p} a_4 - \sigma_m a_5 = 0 \text{ -----}$$

$$\text{----- (5)}$$

We obtain the left eigenvector by solving the following systems of equations (4) is

$$\left(-\frac{\beta_p I_m}{N_p} - \sigma_p\right) b_1 + \frac{\beta_p I_m}{N_p} b_2 - \sigma_p b_3 = 0$$

$$-(\gamma_p + \delta_p + \sigma_p) b_2 + \gamma_p b_3 - \frac{\beta_m S_m}{N_p} b_4 + \frac{\beta_m S_m}{N_p} b_5 = 0$$

$$\varepsilon_p b_1 - \varepsilon_p b_3 = 0$$

$$-\sigma_m b_4 + \frac{B_m I_p}{N_p} b_5 = 0$$

$$\frac{\beta_p S_p}{N_p} b_1 + \frac{B_p S_p}{N_p} b_2 - \sigma_m b_5 = 0 \text{ -----}$$

$$\text{----- (5)}$$

Utilizing the property a.b=1

$$a_1 = \frac{(\gamma_p \sigma_m \sigma_p N_p^3 - \beta_p S_p \sigma_p N_m \beta_m S_m + \beta_p S_p \beta_m^2 S_m I_p) a_2}{\sigma_m \sigma_p N_p^2 (\beta_p I_m - 2 \sigma_p N_p)}$$

$$a_2 = 1, a_3 = \frac{\gamma_p a_2 - \sigma_p a_1}{\varepsilon_p}, a_4 = \frac{-(\beta_m S_m) a_2}{\sigma_m N_p}, a_5 = \frac{(\sigma_p N_p \beta_m S_m - \beta_m^2 S_m I_p) a_2}{\sigma_p N_p^2 \sigma_m}$$

$$b_1 = \frac{\beta_p I_m b_2}{\beta_p I_m + N_p \sigma_p}, b_2 = 1, b_3 = \frac{\beta_p I_m b_2}{\beta_p I_m + N_p \sigma_p},$$

$$b_4 = \frac{\beta_m I_p \beta_p S_p b_2}{\sigma_m N_p (\beta_p I_m + \sigma_p N_p)}, b_5 = \frac{\beta_p S_p (b_2 - b_1)}{\sigma_m N_p}$$

From the conditions of (Castillo et al,2004),

$$\xi = \sum_{k,i,j=1}^3 v_k w_i w_j \frac{\partial^2 F_k}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} (E_0, \Phi)$$

$\varphi = \sum_{k,i=1}^3 v_k w_i \frac{\partial^2 F_k}{\partial x_i \partial \beta} (E_0, \Phi)$ From the result is Positive. Hence $R_0^* >$, the backward bifurcation is existed.

Fuzzy Control System:

In this section, we have analyzed the control of the valuation of the disease of malaria by using fuzzy basic reproduction numbers and Bifurcation Parameter β^* .

i) Case: a(Weak)

In this case, the virus load is weak. (i.e) when $\bar{\phi} + x \leq \phi_{min}$. The fuzzy basic reproduction number R_{OF} is 0. It means the disease will be extinct.

ii) Case: b(Medium)

In this case the virus load is Medium. (i.e) when $\bar{\phi} - x \geq \phi_{min}$ and $\bar{\phi} + x \leq$. There exist virus load ϕ such that R_0 and $R_0(\phi)$ coincide. Furthermore, the average number of secondary cases R_{OF} is higher than the number of secondary cases $R_0(\bar{\phi})$ due to the medium amount of virus.

iii) Case: c(Strong)

In this case, the virus load is Strong. (i.e) when $\bar{\phi} + x \leq \phi_M$ and $\bar{\phi} + x \leq$. Thus, $R_{OF} > 1$; so the disease will be endemic.

Remark:

Backward bifurcation has significant implications for disease control. First, in the presence of backward bifurcation, if $R_0 \approx 1$, the number of infectives jumps significantly from its initial values and equilibrates at high equilibrium numbers rather than increase gradually as R_0 above R^* . Secondly, even if $R_0 < 1$, the disease may Persist if the initial number of infected is sufficiently large. in our

problem will be the transmission of the disease is controlled.

Conclusion:

Analysis has been done on a nonlinear mathematical model of malaria transmission. We have created the local stability of our model's endemic and disease-free equilibriums. Our main goal in this model is to highlight the backward bifurcation. The bifurcation result might be useful in understanding how the disease spreads.

Acknowledgments: We appreciate SRM Institute of Science and Technology's ongoing support of our scientific endeavors.

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